

EVOLUTION OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM AND THEIR IMPACT ON SOCIETY DEVELOPMENT IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the evolution of the education system and its role in the development of society. Educational processes are studied in the historical, cultural and social context, and it is shown how education contributes to the development of society, economic growth and preservation of cultural heritage. The thesis highlights changes, innovations and new methodologies in the education system, as well as their impact on social stability and development. The authors show how the educational system changes at each stage of education in connection with social and economic changes and the impact of these changes on society.

Key words: Educational system, evolution, social development, social stability, innovations, cultural heritage, educational methodologies, economic development, educational processes, education and social changes.

Introduction:

The education system is one of the main elements of any society, it forms the foundation of social, economic and cultural development. Over the past centuries, educational systems have changed and developed, trying to adapt to new requirements and conditions. This process increased the role and importance of education in human life. Education plays an important role not only in imparting knowledge, but also in forming social relations, cultural values and human resources.

Today, the evolution of education systems is developing rapidly under the influence of factors such as globalization, digital technologies and social changes. These changes are aimed at improving the quality of education, making the learning process more interactive and renewing the attitude to education. This thesis analyzes the evolution of educational systems and their impact on the development of society.

Also, news and innovations in the educational process, as well as how they contribute to social stability and economic development of society, are considered. Studying the historical changes of educational systems and how they

play an important role in society helps us to formulate future educational strategies.

Literature review:

Studies on the evolution of the education system and its impact on the development of society include a number of works aimed at studying the relationship of education to social and economic development. These literatures shed light on how educational processes change in historical context, as well as how they affect culture and social structures.

First, there are a number of basic theories related to the evolution of the education system. For example, John Dewey's new approach to education saw education not only as a process of imparting knowledge, but as a process of learning through experience and social interaction. Dewey saw education as a means of social transformation and strengthened the connection between education and society (Dewey, 1916).¹

Second, research on the impact of education on economic growth examines the impact of investment in education on social stability and economic development. Becker (1993) defines education as the main source of human capital and emphasizes the important relationship between education and economic growth. This approach demonstrates the economic benefits of education at the individual and societal levels.²

There is also a large body of literature on the impact of globalization and digital technologies on education systems. International studies such as PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) focus on global changes in education systems by assessing the quality of education between countries³. These studies show how education systems can learn from each other and adapt to global demands (OECD, 2018).

At the same time, there are many scientific theses about innovations and new methodologies in the educational process. This literature emphasizes the need for interactive, collaborative learning and individualized learning (Dron & Anderson, 2014)⁴. New methods of education help to ensure social justice in society and expand educational opportunities for all levels.

The analysis of this literature serves to further deepen our knowledge about the evolution of educational systems and their role in the development of

¹ Dewey, J. (1916). *Democracy and Education: An Introduction to the Philosophy of Education*. Macmillan

² Becker, G. S. (1993). *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education*. University of Chicago Press.

³ OECD. (2018). *PISA 2018 Results (Volume I): What Students Know and Can Do*. OECD Publishing.

⁴ Dron, J., & Anderson, T. (2014). *Teaching Crowds: Learning and Social Media*. Athabasca University Press.

society, and also serves as an important basis for the development of educational strategies in the future.

Discussion:

The evolution of the education system and its impact on the development of society includes many important aspects. Education is not only a process of imparting knowledge, but also serves as the main tool in the development of humanity. Changes in the educational process are closely related to important transformations in the social and economic structure of society.

First of all, Becker's theory of human capital is important in the question of the impact of education on economic growth. Investing in education, as a result, creates a skilled workforce and serves as the main source of economic development. Also, the improvement of the education system helps to ensure social stability. Education plays an important role in creating equal opportunities for all strata, ensuring social justice and increasing economic prosperity.

Innovations in the educational process are seen as a necessary tool for meeting the modern demands of society and acquiring new knowledge. Digital technologies and interactive educational methods help to make the educational process more effective. However, in this process, existing problems of educational systems, such as gaps between existing methodologies and resources, can increase social inequality. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the needs and conditions of all layers when updating educational systems.

In addition, it is important to study how the education system is changing in the process of globalization. Cooperation and exchange of knowledge is necessary to adapt to global requirements and improve the quality of education between countries. These processes ensure that educational systems are adapted to modern conditions and create new opportunities for future generations.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the evolution of the education system and its impact on the development of society is seen as an integral part of social and economic development. Changes in the educational process serve not only the development of individuals, but also the general development of society. Therefore, improving educational systems and adapting them to modern conditions is an important task for all society.

In this thesis, the evolution of the education system and its influence on the development of the society were analyzed in depth. Education, playing an important role in the development of society and economic growth, forms human capital and ensures social stability. Historically, educational systems have changed and adapted to the needs of the times. Innovations and new methodologies are important in making the educational process effective and interactive.

Also, in the process of globalization, changes in education systems and exchange of knowledge between countries help to improve the quality of education. However, existing problems in the field of education can increase social inequality, so it is necessary to take into account the needs of all strata. As a result, it is an important task to further improve and adapt educational systems to modern conditions, create new opportunities for future generations, and ensure the general development of society. Education, not only imparting knowledge, but also as an integral part of social, economic and cultural development, must always be updated and maintain its importance.

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